

PROBLEMS OF CREATING PICTURE DICTIONARIES FOR 5-6 GRADE LITERATURE CLASSES

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Abstract

The article analyzes the scientific basis of the use of modern information technologies, in particular picture dictionaries, in the teaching of literature lessons in the 5th-6th grade from a pedagogical and psychological point of view. Their peculiarities in ensuring the effectiveness of education are discussed. Also, opinions are given about the role of teachers and trainers in ensuring the legality, systematicity and effectiveness of creating new methods, methods, especially picture dictionaries. It is also discussed about the effectiveness of students' mastery of the subject through multimediaization of the educational process. The use of picture dictionaries in the teaching of topics in literature classes of 5-6 grades and some problems in creating picture dictionaries are discussed. The impact of this type of vocabulary on the educational process is explained using Gardner's theory and John Kehoe's visualization technique. In particular, comments are made about the advantages of classic literature examples in teaching.

Key words: *modern information technologies, multimedia tools, pedagogical assistant, psychological factors, Constitution, children's literature, scientific and technical development, literary and pictorial dictionaries, multimediaization.*

Enter

Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan that the issue of creating and improving the national methodology has risen to the level of a vital need known. The reformation process observed in all directions became the foundation for making updates in the fields of methodology and pedagogy. Now deepening the essence of the methodology and becoming involved in the educational process is an important issue in all respects. became No one knows that there is a lack of methods that have a positive effect on the student's thinking and behavior in the circle of new methods, both in revealing the basic content of the educational process and in the educational process, and that the demand for them is increasing inversely proportional to the above indicator. it's not a secret. The question of whether all types of modern information technologies, which combine tradition, research and innovation, are suitable as a tool for teachers and students today is more relevant than ever. Therefore, there is a need to multimediaize the educational process using the picture dictionaries contained in it, giving educational status to the multimedia tools of modern information technologies. is increasing more and more.

It should be emphasized that the problems of deep and effective teaching of literature, special sciences, history of our country and world civilization, foreign languages and modern computer programs to children and young people have not yet been solved in a qualitative and complete way. At this time, it is important to find out how picture dictionaries help schoolchildren, especially in the teaching of literature lessons of the 5th and 6th grades, and,

accordingly, to test such new views in practice. In addition, it will be appropriate to pay attention to the problems of creating such dictionaries and show their solutions.

The main part

First of all, multimediaization of the educational process - in this place, it is intended to create an environment where the use of picture dictionaries in the 5th-6th grade literature classes is provided - it should be noted that the freedom of technical creativity in literary education is also legally confirmed by Article 42 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

"Everyone is guaranteed the freedom of scientific and technical creativity, the right to use cultural achievements. The state takes care of the cultural, scientific and technical development of society." [Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan 1992, 34]

Legally approved freedom of technical creativity creates a basis for teachers and trainers, methodologists, creators to apply innovations in the educational process, create new methods and methods, and of course prepare and use picture dictionaries for literature classes. At this point, it is important to know how effective these types of dictionaries are in literary education and how necessary they are for students and teachers.

In addition, the introduction of the use of picture dictionaries - taking into account their entry into the ranks of multimedia tools in the range of modern pedagogical tools - into the educational process is considered important in two ways:

I. Pedagogical in terms of :

1) forms the student's personal competencies such as reading, understanding, explanation, analysis - in this process, the words learned with the help of picture dictionaries are of great importance;

2) they act as a "pedagogical assistant" for the teacher during the lesson - they also help the teacher to convey to the students words that are difficult for the students to understand, which are found in classic literature samples. Because this process is problematic not only for students, but also for teachers;

3) fills the gaps in the thinking of low-absorbing or all students based on the principles of visibility and instruction - in contrast to "dry" memorization, there is no gap in the minds of students, this gap is filled with the help of pictures;

4) picture dictionaries help the reader at any time, that is, it can always be carried on mobile devices;

5) they can be used for the purpose of preparation in the process of preparing for various exams, it will be difficult for applicants who want to enter higher educational institutions to remember such words, in such a situation it can be a good helper for them;

6) in particular, it can be a solution to the problems related to remembering words that children have the most difficulty in teaching classic literature examples presented in 5-6 grade literature textbooks.

II. Psychologically:

1) the use of picture dictionaries, which are considered close to modern information technologies, is suitable for children's age characteristics, because at this age, students are still at the age of play, and pictures and visual aids are interesting for them;

2) It is important in attracting their attention during the lesson, it also ensures long-term memory in terms of memory properties, it is difficult for students to focus their attention for 20 minutes, and then the proposed method can be effective. Words learned through

picture dictionaries form long-term memory, not short-term memory. Words memorized in this way will be remembered later when viewing the image;

3) it is appropriate to use these technologies according to the children's character, because at this age students are interested in games, etc.

If we look at the topics in the 5th grade literature textbook, there are many examples that bring children back to the museum. These lessons introduce them to the first concepts of our classic literature, theoretical information, examples of fiction. For example, in the section called "The Capital of Classical Literature" there is an excerpt from the epic "Hayrat ul-Abror" by Hazrat Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the ghazal estate, - the chapter on straightness and crookedness and "Sher bilan durraj" " story is presented, and we also find theoretical information about classical works . The difficulty of the section for children is characterized by the fact that the words found in the examples of our classic literature are unfamiliar to them. It is with this feature in mind that it is useful for us to explain new words to children through images. Because images are imprinted in children's memory, affecting both linguistic and visual intelligence. Since the multimedia tools themselves are part of the illustrations, it is possible to use all the multimedia tools during the lesson - dictionaries, which are its main component. Graphics, color images and "animated" images - animated films are needed especially in the teaching of the above topics in the educational process. Picture dictionaries are in high demand in teaching this section. For example:

Mistar – chizg'ich

When creating such picture dictionaries, dictionaries created in different languages such as Uzbek - English, English - Uzbek, Russian - Uzbek can be used as examples. The reason is that the need for picture dictionaries has arisen at this point. We know that pictures are equally understood and accepted by people who speak all languages, they do not need translation. Therefore, it is more logical to use pictures to memorize the words that are unfamiliar to the students in our classical literature. With this, a suitable

solution to one of the main problems faced by students in understanding classic literature samples has been found.

, it is also clear that there are a number of problems in bringing picture dictionaries into the educational process and giving them an educational status. In fact, since multimedia tools are elements of the media sphere, giving them an educational character is the primary problem, and this is solved by the content of picture dictionaries and, in essence, the mastery of the topic in literature classes.

Secondly, not all words found in our textbooks have images, for example the word "ila", its explanation is "bilan", but this auxiliary word cannot be represented in an image. There are many examples of such words. In this regard, we cannot make a large-scale impact on the memory of students with picture

Durroj – kaptarning bir turi, qirg'ovul

dictionaries. That is, it is not possible to create picture dictionaries of all the words listed in literature textbooks. And the number of words with images is not that great. Nevertheless, it is advisable to continue using picture dictionaries, taking into account that the goal is quality, not quantity.

In fact, as mentioned above, picture dictionaries are referred to in different languages . (see page 3) [Hojiyev, Muhiddinova, Kambarov, Mirzayev 2013: 10]

These dictionaries aim to attract children's attention by providing pictures of words with images, and to penetrate their thinking with both visual and verbal memory. This is the goal of creating picture dictionaries in literature classes. But in the dictionaries of different languages above, the possibilities are much wider, and it is possible to create a much richer resource than the words with images. Literary-picture dictionaries are limited in this regard. However, the existing resource can also be used as a visual tool. Although there are no words with sufficient images for the dictionary, it will be possible to show examples of prepared dictionaries as visual aids in literature classes. Perhaps, if picture dictionaries are created not only for 5-6th grade literature classes, but also for 5-11th grade literature classes, then it will be possible to create a much larger vocabulary.

The importance of using dictionaries with images of cartoon characters that are interesting for children is that in these dictionaries, modern images intersect at one point with

words used in our classic literature. It can also be considered as a form of integration. Now children learn words quickly and easily through fun pictures. Theoretical information is also explained on the basis of visibility. There may be some objections to the fact that the characters found in our classic literature are embodied in the eyes of children like cartoon characters. But for 5th-6th graders, the characters of the cartoons they have seen before are very well known and well-remembered for the students of the 5th-6th grade, and the donkey can come to life in their imaginations, only the character of the donkey from the cartoon that they loved or saw only once.

Picture dictionaries can also be used in the teaching of Muhammadsharif Gulkhani and his work "Zarbulmasal". In this place, too, in the teaching of the work "Zarbulmasal" in the critical-comic direction,

NAJJOR

Najjor – duradgor

which artistically expresses the reality of its time, it is typical of the current era. using images works well. Below are examples of

ZOG'

Zog' – qarg'a

illustrated dictionaries for some words found in the excerpt from "Zarbulmasal" in the textbook:

Another problem faced in the creation of picture dictionaries is the selection of pictures with aesthetic taste.

Let's say there are thousands of pictures of geese, and out of them, the one that will stay the longest in the child's memory and at the same time reveal the character of the goose in the work of art. to be able to choose the picture to take depends on the skill of the creator of the dictionary, in this regard, cooperation between teacher of literature and the designer is important in the development of literary-educational picture dictionaries. If the designer meets the quality of the painting, the above mentioned two conditions - to remain in the reader's memory for a long time and at the same time fully reveal the character in the artwork. It is the responsibility of the teacher-pedagogue to choose the picture to be taken. That way, it is possible to ensure the quality of creating literary and pictorial dictionaries.

Creators who want the words listed in picture dictionaries to be closer and more understandable to children can enrich them linguistically. For example, for the pictorial dictionary "sangpusht - turtle", it can be further enriched by giving the definition of turtle:

QOZ

Qoz – g'oz

the

SANGPUSHT

Sangpusht – toshbaqa

A turtle is a reptile whose body is cup-shaped and surrounded by a bony shell.

This method can be used to prepare other dictionaries. At the same time, students see unfamiliar words through images and learn new information about this word.

It is also effective to interpret the meaning of these types of dictionaries using visual intelligence. This is because they are absorbed mainly through the eyes. Howard Gardner talks about this in his theory of multiple intelligences. According to him, people have not only one intelligence, but many types of intelligence. Gardner divides these types of intelligence into eight and calls one of them visual intelligence.

Hakim – tabib, shifokor

seeing , we notice objects and events around us, observe their movement and change, learn their shape, color, size and location. Reading, writing, drawing, watching, driving, learning, learning a craft and all other human activities are related to vision. A person receives almost 90% of the information he receives from the outside world through his eyes. [Mavlonov, Tilavov, Aminov, 2019: 159] The fact that most of the information that a person receives from the outside

world is received through the eyes is also a proof that the use of picture dictionaries in literature lessons has a good effect.

Visual-seeing it is a general human intellectual ability, characterized by the ability to imagine in the human mind, to see the big picture clearly, engineers or artists are the owners of great imagination and fantasy. [Rakhmanov 2014: 262] The strength of visual-vision intelligence is that the world of imagination is enriched in it, people with well-developed intelligence are the owners of high fantasy.

In the activation of this process , the influence of animation technologies is clearly visible . As animations aim to "animate" graphics , the reader perceives them directly visually. In the methodology, this concept is also explained by the term "image memory". The essence of this term is that the child begins to learn creative thinking through "image memory" as a result of the influence of animated films on this type of intelligence. At the core of his visual mental ability lays the groundwork for another ability - the ability to think creatively . All of these create a chain and have a good effect on the student's mastery of the lesson and the subject.

TEVA

Teva – tuya

Picture dictionaries also create a visualization process in students' minds. John Kehoe discussed the power of this technique in his theory.

Visualization technique is the formation of a visual image of the situations you want to happen . Visualization is considered very child-friendly because it takes advantage of children's already very active imagination and directs it toward the positive self. It doesn't matter if it's about passing a test or making a new friend, this technique can produce amazing results . Children have a very strong imagination, so they take the idea of visualization lightly. [Kehoe, Fisher 2017: 38-39]

This technique is usually necessary for a person to work on himself, expand his capabilities, and develop as a person. But it is not without its educational value. Because visualization also helps to revive images that are imprinted in the minds of students. A child can enrich the images he sees in picture dictionaries with his imagination. Let's say that the reader who sees the image of the durraj after reading the work combines the image and the content and brings the durraj in the picture together with the durraj in the text in his mind. This technique is called visualization, and it works very well with children. Because there is nothing that cannot be realized in their imagination, that's why they are the owners of the strongest fantasy.

In addition, the information received through k is stored in the human brain both voluntarily and involuntarily. In many cases, a person cannot forget what he saw with his own eyes, whether he wants to or not. The use of illustrations, educational animations, videos , picture dictionaries in the course of the lesson expands students' visualization capabilities.

Xar – eshak

Picture dictionaries are also important from the point of view that today among the students studying in the city, there are also children who do not have enough visual thinking about "donkey". Because there is a high probability that they have not seen the live state of a donkey like the children living in the village. For such students, such dictionaries serve as both new words and new images. Therefore, the use of picture dictionaries in education has a positive effect on children's mastery of the subject and interest in the lesson.

Preparing an electronic version of picture dictionaries is also very effective for the educational process. Such dictionaries, which can be stored on mobile devices at any time and in any situation, are useful to students. Only for this, it is necessary to use not only the dictionaries of the 5th-6th grade literature classes, but all the dictionaries in the school literature textbooks. This is because words with more images gain a wider range and are more effective to use. Preparation of the electronic version of the picture dictionaries also provides an opportunity to use the animated forms of the pictures in them. With its "movement" and proximity to videos, this multimedia tool engages students, keeps them focused on the lesson, and helps them remember those words better, boosting their mastery rates. In addition, the ability to save it on mobile devices is convenient for everyone.

It depends on the skill of the teacher to be able to correctly solve the problems encountered in the preparation of literary and pictorial dictionaries, to be able to use them effectively and systematically, even if the scope of opportunities they provide is not so wide. In addition, it is necessary to remember that dictionaries of this type are first of all a helper for the pedagogue, they should be used as a means of content delivery, multimedia tools , picture dictionaries are not a basis, but a tool. Deferring from substance to mere form can have a negative impact on the quality of education. In literary education in particular, content should always be primary and form should be instrumental in its delivery.

Summary

It should not be forgotten that picture dictionaries, which are considered a small form of multimediaization of the educational process, are appropriate and necessary during the lesson. It is required to use only in places. Abu Rayhan Beruni emphasized these aspects long ago. His views on this issue are still relevant. The opinions of the scientist about the ways and methods of acquiring scientific knowledge are still relevant today. The following goals stated by the thinker can be achieved by providing knowledge to students using literary-picture dictionaries in 5-6 grade literature classes:

- not to bore the reader;
- not teaching the same thing or the same subject in education;
- coherence, consistency;
- analysis and comparison;
- repetition;
- focus on interesting, mainly visual presentation of new topics

to give [Hashimov, Nishonova 2005: 86]

Pictures do not bore the student, they are interested in the lesson. It brings to life the scenes in his imagination and remains in his memory for a long time. In imparting knowledge, it avoids memorizing the same thing, that is, the same words, and serves to deliver them to the student in a different way. The combination of the images you see with the content provides coherence. Perhaps, by comparing the pictures with the characters in the work, the students can develop their logical and critical thinking, and by analyzing the images, they can be better imprinted in their memories. Repetition skills are created by strengthening the vocabulary seen in the textbook with images. It is also possible to increase students' interest in science by explaining new topics in a visual way.

Literature

Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1992. - - P. 34.

Hajiyev A., Muhiddinova H., Kambarov N., Mirzayev R. Uzbek-Russian-English dictionary. Tashkent: Teacher, 2013. - B.10.

Mavlonov O., Tilavov T., Aminov B. Biology (Man and his health). - Tashkent: "Teacher" publishing house, 2019. - P. 159 .

Rahmonov Sh. Learn to learn, perfect memory, and rediscover your brain's abilities. - Tashkent: New generation, 2014. - P. 262.

Kehoe J., Fisher N. The power of the mind - in the service of children. - Tashkent: Davr Press, 2017, - P.38-39.

Hashimov K., Nishonova S. History of pedagogy. Part II. - Tashkent: Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2005. - P. 86.